

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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USE OF THE ADVANCED EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES OF FARMING AND HOUSEHOLDS

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Abstract: This article analyzes the types of products grown on farms and homesteads, changes in their productivity, the volume of gross products obtained, the factors affecting them, as well as the prospects for increasing the efficiency of production on farms and homesteads. A proposal for efficient use of land and recommendations are given.

Key words: agriculture, farms, homesteads, land use, productivity, gross output, forecasting.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada dehqon xo'jaliklari va tomorqa yerlarida yetishtiriladigan mahsulot turlari, ularning hosildorlik darajasidagi o'zgarishi, olingan yalpi mahsulot hajmi, ularga ta'sir etuvchi omillar tahlil qilingan, shuningdek, dehqon xo'jaliklari va tomorqa yerlarida mahsulot ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini oshirish istiqbollari, yerdan unumli foydalanish bo'yicha taklif va tavsiyalar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: qishloq xo'jaligi, dehqon xo'jaliklari, tomorqa yerlar, yerdan foydalanish, samaradorlik, yalpi mahsulot hajmi, prognozlash.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются виды продукции, выращиваемой в дехканских и приусадебных хозяйствах, изменения её продуктивности, объёмы получаемой валовой продукции, факторы, влияющие на них, а также перспективы повышения эффективности производства в дехканских и приусадебных хозяйствах. Предложены меры по эффективному использованию земли и даны рекомендации.

Ключевые слова: сельское хозяйство, дехканские хозяйства, сельскохозяйственные угодья, землепользование, продуктивность, валовая продукция, прогнозирование.

INTRODUCTION

In Uzbekistan, agricultural and horticultural activities are gaining importance in ensuring the country's food security. In the future, it is necessary to study the experience of developed foreign countries in the development of a plan of programs and measures related to the sustainable development of economic entities. As a result of researching and summarizing the experience of these countries, one of the main goals is to take into account the laws that have a positive effect on the development of agriculture, to introduce them, and to eliminate those that have a negative result. In foreign practice, there are two models of organizing agricultural entities: American and European model. The American model of development (Sharing) is characteristic of the USA, Canada, Australia and New Zealand and is leading the world market. Farms developed on the basis of the European model were developed in direct connection with processes such as attracting investments and capital accumulation in agriculture.

The experience of foreign countries in the development of agriculture, in particular, the forms of economic management, their property relations and institutional foundations researched the experience of foreign countries in the development of farms and horticultural activities and proposed to implement them in the conditions of the republic and recommendations are developed by S.A. Alekseeva, S.D. Vlasov, N.V. Klimova, A.G. Nikonov, E.N. Petrukhina, Yu. Researched in the works of foreign scientists such as I. Sigidov, A. T. Stadnik, L. I. Ushvitsky, O. A. Frolova, M. N. Kabanenko. Also, scientists of our republic N.S. Khushmatov, F.Egamberdiev, R.Kh.Ergashev, S.N.Khamraeva, G.T.Samieva.

We know, the use of the Sharing model will have a positive effect in the development of the activities of farmers and households in agriculture. The reason is that peasants and homesteads operate on a smaller scale compared to farms, and they have limited opportunities to attract a large amount of equipment and technology.

Table 1.4. The share of small economic entities in the agriculture of some foreign countries in 2023¹.

Share of small farms in the USA, %					
	Wheat	Beets	Fruits	Vegetables	Potatoes
Farming	1.2	75	98	80	28
Other farms	98.8	25	2	20	72
Share of small farms in Germany, %					
Farming	2	35	88	90	-
Other farms	98	65	12	10	-
Share of small Christian (farm) farms in Russia, %					
Small Farm	-	60	98	95	40
Other farms	100	40	2	5	60
Share of small farms in Japan, %					
Farming	40.2	-	90.2	82	49
Other farms	59.8	-	9.8	18	51

Sharing is the practice of several farms pooling their resources and sharing equipment, raw materials, machinery, labor and other resources. In agriculture, Sharing can be especially useful for homesteads and farms that cannot always purchase and maintain their own equipment or employ sufficient labor [1]. In most European countries, especially in Germany, Great Britain, France and other developed countries, Sharing technology is widely used in order to increase the competitiveness of small commodity farms and reduce production costs.

Among the foreign countries with developed agriculture, China first started in 1949 and later in 1978, in Xiaogang, 21 families were given land for farming, and then peasant and homestead farms were widely introduced. 180 million were rented to families for 1-3 years, then for 50 years and longer. Since 1981, 98 percent of arable land has been transferred to peasant farms, grain export has been launched. Chinese President Deng Xiaoping announced the policy of "Agriculture First".

The reforms carried out in foreign countries regarding land and its purposeful use in agriculture led to a change in the form of land ownership, a reduction of the state's monopoly right, and an expansion of the range of its users.

In particular, Bulgaria adopted the Law "On Land" in 1992, which aims to create a free land market in the country.

In Romania, another country with a strong focus on agriculture, the 1991 Land Law is still in force. According to it, each family living in rural areas will be given the right to own land from 10 to 100 hectares, and each person - no less than 0.5 hectares. From the date of entry into force of this law, peasants' homestead lands have become their private lands. Therefore, persons who received land in this form are exempted from paying land tax for a period of 8 years. It should be noted that all landowners are obliged to use agricultural land in a purposeful and rational manner, as stipulated in the Romanian legislation.

Land reforms in the agriculture of the Czech Republic and Slovakia were carried out gradually. In these countries, the law "On Land" adopted in 1991 defines relations related to land [2]. All owners who use land and other agricultural property as defined in this law are recognized as tenants. These countries have a large share of agricultural holdings and are leading the way in ensuring food security.

The current system of land use in Italian agriculture was formed by the land reform carried out in the 1950s. The main goal of this reform was to give up the monopoly of large landowners over land and redistribute it to peasant farms as a result of returning the land belonging to them to the state. The peasant farms operating in this country appear as agricultural workers who work directly on the land.

According to the law adopted in the 19th century, the principle of free choice of land is still valid in Australia, which has a developed agricultural network. In the early years of the Act, this principle provided that each Australian citizen could own between 200 and 800 hectares of land, depending on the productivity of the land. At the moment, the amount of land given to applicants has decreased somewhat. Along with the sale of plots of land, the system of leasing land is widespread in the agriculture of this country [3].

10 percent of Canada's population (more than 3 million people) has a low income, and one in ten families with children under the age of 6 are food insecure. About 8 percent of the total number of families, that is, 800,000 families, live below the level of food security. Since 2/3 of the population has weight problems, the

1 Informations of FAO

use of natural products grown on farms and farms is important for ensuring food security [4]. The land area for agriculture is 70 mln. hectare, and 15% of the economically active population is employed in agriculture, and 9% of the gross domestic product is cultivated in the agricultural sector. In Canada, the producers of agricultural products are called small farmers, and they mainly lead in the production of grains and cereal products, potatoes and fruits. The main goal of expanding the activities of small farmers (peasants) in this country is to develop entrepreneurship among the population.

In our opinion, the following conclusion can be reached regarding the advanced experience of foreign countries in ensuring food safety among the world's population and ways of using them in Uzbekistan:

Intensive and extensive improvement of the production of food products in peasant and homestead farms of the Republic of Uzbekistan, acceleration of growth dynamics, implementation of some experiences of agriculturally developed countries in achieving excellent economic efficiency will have a good effect.

First, it is necessary to expand the system of clustering, which is the experience of the USA, in the activities of peasant farms and landowners. Because there are many opportunities for growing products in farmers' and homesteads. Secondly, in order to ensure food security among the population in the United States, it is appropriate to create and improve rational nutrition and healthy lifestyle programs in our country based on social programs aimed at providing the primary needs of the poor, children and pensioners. In particular, the establishment of measures to provide free milk products to children under 3 years of age will serve to strengthen the foundations of a healthy future.

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